

**Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of some
5-Aryl-2-[N-(5-nitrofurfurylidene)amino]-
and 5-Aryl-2-(N-thiocarbonylamino)-
1,3,4-oxadiazoles**

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OXADIAZOLES are known to possess various anti-
microbial activities¹. Nitrofurans are recognised
antimicrobial agents² as are the thioureas^{3,4}. These

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observations prompted us to prepare the title compounds and screen for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

The starting material 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles¹ (**2a**–**i**) were synthesised (Scheme 1) from substituted benzaldehydes (**1a**–**i**) via their semicarbazones. Treatment of **2** with 5-nitro-2-furaldehyde in dry benzene in presence of piperidine afforded the corresponding 5-aryl-2-[N-(5-nitrofurfurylidene)amino]-1,3,4-oxadiazoles⁶ (**3a**–**i**). Further treatment of **2** with benzoyl isothiocyanate gave the corresponding 5-aryl-2-[N-(N-benzoylthiocarbonylamino)]-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**4a**–**i**) which when refluxed with 10% aqueous NaOH solution furnished the corresponding 5-aryl-2-(N-thiocarbonylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles^{6,7} (**5a**–**i**). The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of elemental analyses, ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral data.

- 2-5a**, R=3-OEt-4-OMe **f**; R=2-OEt-4-OMe-5-Et
b; R=4-OEt-3-OMe **g**; R=4-OEt-2-OMe-5-Et
c; R=2,4-(OMe)₂-5-Et **h**; R=2,4-(OMe)₂-5-n-Pr
d; R=2,4-(OEt)₂-5-Et **i**; R=2,4-(OEt)₂-5-n Pr
e; R=2,5-(OEt)₂-4-Et

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) 5-nitrofurfuraldehyde in dry benzene, piperidine, (ii) Ph. CO NCS, (iii) 10% aqueous NaOH

The compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity against gram-positive bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram-negative bacterium *Escherichia coli* and the fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* using agar diffusion technique⁸ at 1 mg and 100 μg ml⁻¹ (disc size 5 mm) using mycostatin and streptomycin respectively as standards. Out of 18 compounds tested, compounds **3a**, **c**–**f**, **h** and **i** exhibited a low degree of inhibition against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a Toshniwal electrically heated apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian T-60A spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol 300 spectrometer.

2-Amino-5-(3-ethoxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (2a): To a well-stirred suspension of 3-ethoxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde semicarbazone (2.0 g) and sodium acetate (3.3 g) in glacial acetic acid, was added bromine (0.6 ml in 5 ml of glacial acetic acid) dropwise with continuous stirring. The mixture

was stirred further for 15 min and then poured into cold water. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (1.5 g, 75%), m.p. 190–91° (lit.¹ 191°).

Other compounds (**2b**–**i**) were prepared similarly (yield in %, m.p. (lit.¹ m.p.)): **2b**, 70, 200° (201°); **2c**, 75, 204° (205°); **2d**, 75, 197° (197°); **2e**, 75, 202° (203°); **2f**, 70, 179° (179°); **2g**, 75, 182° (183°); **2h**, 65, 183° (185°); **2i**, 80, 207° (207°).

5-(3-Ethoxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-2-[N-(5-nitrofurfurylidene)amino]-1,3,4-oxadiazole (3a): A mixture of **2** (0.235 g, 1.0 mmol) and 5-nitro-2-furaldehyde (0.141 g, 1.0 mmol) in dry benzene (50 ml) and piperidine (3–4 drops) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h, removing water azeotropically. The mixture was then cooled and the resulting solid was recrystallised from acetic acid, (65%, 0.232 g), m.p. 187° (Found: C, 53.42; H, 3.90; N, 15.35. C₁₆H₁₄N₄O₆ requires: C, 53.63; H, 3.91; N, 15.64%); *m/z* 358 (*M*⁺); *ν*_{max} 1 615 (C=N), 1 515 (N=O assym.), 1 345 (N=O sym.), 1 260 (aryl, alkyl –C–O–C– sym.), 960 (–C–O–C) and 840 cm⁻¹ (C–NO₂); *δ* (TFA) 1.21 (3H, t, OCH₂CH₃), 3.75 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.9 (2H, q, OCH₂CH₃), 7.05 (1H, d, *J* 3.66 Hz, nitrofuryl-H), 7.13 (1H, s, ArH), 7.27 (1H, d, *J* 3.66 Hz, nitrofuryl-H), 7.35 (1H, d, *J* 1.8 Hz, ArH), 7.68 (1H, d, *J* 1.8 Hz, ArH), 9.1 (1H, s, N=CH).

Other compounds (**3b**–**i**) were prepared similarly (yield in %, m.p.): **3b**, 67, 185°; **3c**, 66, 196°; **3d**, 68, 209°; **3e**, 63, 206°; **3f**, 64, 176°; **3g**, 68, 210°; **3h**, 65, 202°; **3i**, 69, 180°.

5-Aryl-2-[N-(N-benzoylthiocarbonylamino)]-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4a–i): A vigorously hot stirred solution of ammonium thiocyanate (0.076 g, 1.0 mmol) in dry acetone (20 ml) was added dropwise to benzoyl chloride (0.135 g, 1.0 mmol) in dry acetone (10 ml). The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for 1.5 h and to it was added an equimolar quantity of the appropriate **3a**–**i** (1.0 mmol) in dry acetone. The mixture was refluxed for 6 h on a water-bath. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and diluted with ice-cold water (50 ml) to yield the products (45–60%).

5-(3-Ethoxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-2-(N-thiocarbonylamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (5a): The crude **4a** (0.2 g) was refluxed with 10% aqueous NaOH solution (10 ml) for 15 min and then treated with concentrated HCl until acidic to precipitate both benzoic acid and the title compound (**5a**). The reaction mixture was made basic (pH 9) with NH₄OH solution to dissolve the benzoic acid. The resulting solid (**5a**) was recrystallised from CHCl₃–petroleum ether, (0.084 g, 60%), m.p. 151–52° (Found: C, 49.31; H, 4.69; N, 19.00. C₁₂H₁₄N₄O₃S requires: C, 48.97; H, 4.76; N, 19.04%); *m/z* 294 (*M*⁺); *ν*_{max} 3 450, 3 350–3 140 (NH and NH₂), 1 650 (NH bending) and 1 610 cm⁻¹ (C=N); *δ* (CDCl₃) 1.52 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 3.91 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.16 (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 4.27 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.21 (1H, s, ArH), 7.32 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, ArH) and 7.62 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, ArH).

Other compounds (5b-i) were prepared similarly (yield in %, m.p.): 5b, 55, 155°; 5c, 56, 148°; 5d, 54, 163°; 5e, 52, 165°; 5f, 60, 158°; 5g, 55, 160°; 5h, 57, 167°; 5i, 53, 172°.

References

1. P. L. KACHROO, R. GUPTA, S. C. GUPTA and A. K. GUPTA, *Nat. Acad. Sci. Lett.*, 1990, **13**, 125.
2. P. E. THOMPSON, *Ann. Rev. Pharmacol.*, 1967, **7**, 77
3. P. E. EISMAN, E. A. KONOPEKA and R. L. MAYER, *Am. Rev. Tubercul.*, 1954, **70**, 121.
4. D. R. SHRIDHAR, K. S. RAO, K. RASTOGI and S. S. GANDHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 761.
5. M. GHOSH and B. G. CHATTERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 457.
6. GRAMACHANDRIAH and K. K. REDDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 185.
7. M. VON DORT, R. CEUBIG and R. E. COUNSEL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1987, **30**, 1241.
8. R. S. VERMA and W. L. NOBLES, *J. Pharm. Soc.*, 1968, **1**, 1801.